
**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL
COMPETENCIES AMONG STUDENTS**

Kushbakova Vasila Namozovna

Associate professor of the faculty of Foreign languages
TashSPU named after Nizami

Annotatsiya: Maqolada talabalarda muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish va kasbiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda muloqot madaniyatining ahamiyati va dolzarbligi haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit soʻz: Muloqot madaniyati, kommunikativ, kompetensiya,

Annotation: The article examines the importance and relevance of communication culture in the development of communication culture among students and the formation of professional competencies.

Key words: communicative competence, communication, skills

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается значение и актуальность культуры общения в развитии культуры общения у учащихся и формировании профессиональных компетенций.

Ключевые слова: культура общения, коммуникативная, компетенция

Communicative culture is an essential component of a person’s basic culture, reflecting their willingness to shape their own life and establish harmonious relationships with the surrounding world and within it.

I. Rydanova proposes the concept of a culture of communicative engagement, which encompasses the following aspects:

1. Sufficiency of students' responses to the actions and interactions of the teacher and the synchronization of joint activities.
2. Emotional and cognitive engagement, creating an environment for creative exploration and collaboration.
3. Adherence to ethical standards in professional and interpersonal interactions between teachers and students.

V.N. Yanushevsky proposed a competence-based approach to the analysis of communicative culture. Psychological scientists have emphasized the significance of communication in shaping an individual's personality. Specifically, psychologist B.P. Ananyev explored this topic in depth in his work, “Man as a Subject of Knowledge,” arguing that the mastery of various elements of knowledge is crucial for successful assimilation. He also notes that knowledge acquisition is achieved through communication. B. G. Ananev provides reasonable justification for the fact that

individuals do not develop if they fail to transfer information to one another, and do not exchange experiences via communication. There are various definitions of the term "communication". Communication can be defined as the interaction in information exchange between two or more individuals, which has a cognitive or affective-evaluative nature. Alternatively, communication is a complex process of establishing and maintaining connections between individuals, arising from a need for collaborative activities and involving the exchange of information. It entails the development of a shared way of interacting, perceiving, and understanding another individual. This is the most comprehensive and accurate definition for the term "communication."

Communication is a complex process of establishing and maintaining relationships between individuals, arising from the need for cooperation in various activities. It involves the transfer of information between people involved in joint endeavors, while also taking into account the interactive aspect of these relationships.

The concept of communication differs from that of communication in that it refers to the broader process of interaction and exchange between individuals, whereas communication specifically refers to the transfer of information.

Communication refers to the transfer of information between living and non-living systems. The exchange of signals among animals and human interaction with technical devices are all examples of communication. However, communication can only occur between humans. A human infant becomes a fully-fledged member of society through communication and interaction with others, gaining social experience and cultural knowledge. Communication is the primary form of social activity occurring during ontogenesis (individual development).

Throughout their activities, new relationships and bonds are formed between individuals. Consequently, activity and communication are intrinsically linked.

Assessing the educational and didactic significance of pedagogical communication, Leontiev highlights the following aspects: active pedagogical communication is key to students' acquisition of knowledge and learning in the educational process conducted by teachers and the teaching staff as a whole, as well as the creative nature of educational activities. It creates optimal conditions for the development of students' personalities, provides an optimal emotional atmosphere in the educational setting, and helps prevent the emergence of psychological barriers. Education is an essential tool for managing socio-psychological processes among children and ensuring the rational application of teachers' pedagogical abilities in the learning process.

In pedagogical practice, communication functions as a means for addressing student education based on contemporary standards, as well as a system for socio-educational support in educational settings.

The interpersonal aspect of communication refers to a person's interactions with their immediate environment, including other individuals and communities they will be involved with throughout their life.

The cognitive aspect of communication enables us to gather information about the identity of the interlocutor, their personality traits, and expectations regarding their behavior, as well as other aspects relevant to their character.

The communicative and informational aspects of communication involve the exchange of ideas, interests, emotions, and interactions between individuals with different perspectives. The emotional aspect of communication relates to the feelings and moods of the participants in personal interactions. The conative (or behavioral) aspect of communication helps to resolve internal and external conflicts in the perspectives of the interlocutors.

Communication performs various functions. Different authors distinguish different communication functions. G. M. Andreeva refers to communicative, interactive, and prospective functions. M. I. Ikkeyev refers to information-communication, management-communication, prospective-productive, and affective-expressive (emotional expression) functions. A. A. Brody: instrumental, syndicated, persuasive, and self-expression functions. Instrumental communication is the primary function of communication that involves transmitting important information in order to carry out an action. This task is closely related but not identical to a unifying or syndicating function. The immediate objectives of most communication acts are to establish and strengthen connections between individuals and groups, both large and small.

Self-expression is an essential component of this process, as it is inherently linked to the objective of fostering solidarity and facilitating communication. Self-expression plays a significant role in creative activities, as it allows individuals to express themselves and connect with others.

Additionally, the task of developing and implementing communication methods and evaluation criteria that are based on activity is crucial. This task forms the foundation of education, as through communication, individuals can develop their personalities and learn about the world around them.

L.A. Karpenko purposefully identifies eight different communication tasks:

- communicative-receiving and transmitting messages, as well as establishing communication as a state of mutual trust between two parties;
- informative-exchange of messages, ideas, goals, solutions, etc.;
- motivating-stimulating activity of the communication partner, directing him to perform certain actions;
- managerial-mutual orientation and coordination of actions in the organization of joint activities;

- the task of perception is not only to perceive and understand the essence of the transmitted information in a proportionate way, but also the partners mutually understand each other (desires, inclinations, experiences, states, etc.);

- a motiv–awakening of the necessary emotional experiences in the partner (“exchange of sensations”), as well as a change from his through personal experiences and states;

- establishment of relationships, awareness and fixation of one's position in role, level, work, interpersonal and other communication systems within society in which an individual is expected to function;

- influence, a change in the state, behavior, and personally significant aspects of a partner, including desires, inclinations, thoughts, decisions, ideas, needs, actions, and activity, etc.

B.F. Lomov proposes the following communication objectives:

- Information and communication, involving the processes of receiving and transmitting information.

- Managerial-communicative objectives, related to the mutual adjustment of actions in order to carry out cooperative activities.

- Affective and communicative objectives, which are related to the realm of human emotions and address the need to change one's emotional state.

These objectives are realized in the context of real-life communication.

It should be noted that, in the daily interactions of individuals, there are several types of communication that can be distinguished:

- Masked communication is a formal form of communication where the aim is not to understand or consider the individuality of the other person. Instead, formal language and expressions are used in order to conceal true feelings, intentions, and relationships. This type of communication often involves the use of a set of polite and ambitious masks, as well as standardized facial expressions and gestures.

- In contrast, ordinary communication involves evaluating another person as either a necessary or an interfering entity. If they are seen as necessary, active engagement may occur, while if they are perceived as interfering, attempts to discourage or repel them may be made, or threatening or rude language may be used.

- Formal role-based communication refers to communication at the level of the social roles of the partners (e.g., boss-subordinate, seller-buyer, service personnel-client), and is characterized by the presence of certain rules and expectations that guide the content and mode of communication.

- Guided communication aims to take advantage of the personality of the interlocutor through various techniques (e.g., flattery, intimidation, deception), and is not concerned with the subject matter.

The essence of guided communication is that it is not related to the content, as individuals express opinions that are common in such situations, rather than their own thoughts.

- Aerial communication is a means of communication for the purpose of communicating.

During spiritual, interpersonal communication with friends, one can discuss any topic and understand one another through facial expressions, tone, and body language.

Communication is a complex process. Before engaging in communication, an individual sets several goals. Specifically, they plan the purpose of the communication, when and where it will take place, and with whom it will occur. Russian educator V.A. Kan-Kalik argues that the structure of a teacher's pedagogical communication is based on three main aspects:

1. The prognostic phase (modeling): In this stage, the teacher models future communication with their students.

2. Communicative phase: This is the actual process of establishing direct communication during initial interactions with students.

3. Pedagogical phase: The teacher's behavior and teaching skills should be directly focused on managing communication.

- Analysis of results: Analysis of the implemented communication, modelling of future activities, with an objective assessment of achievements and areas for improvement.

Based on the opinions of scientists, these areas of communication can be described as follows:

During the modeling phase, it is essential for the audience to respond to all patterns and study the psychological characteristics of each individual student. It is also important to anticipate and address potential difficulties that may arise during the learning process, so that communication can be based on mutual understanding and interaction. This means that communication should not only reflect the personality of the educator, but also the personality of each student.

At the stage of communication, it is important to master techniques for engaging the class in interactive activities, meeting their interests, allowing them to freely express their opinions, and using various methods to positively influence their consciousness. The teacher's role at this stage of the learning process is crucial in shaping skills to direct educational efforts in a particular direction, support student initiative, organize fair communication between formal and informal teachers, and adapt to the opinions of the group in accordance with real-life circumstances.

When analyzing the results of the educational activities, the teacher must be able to apply them critically in future educational activities. This involves taking into

account both the successes and shortcomings in their assessment, in order to ensure the unity of goals, plans, and outcomes. In the educational process, the teacher should also be able to exercise initiative in organizing communication with students and managing it.

References:

1. Husanov B., G`ulomov B. “Muomala madaniyati” T.: Ta’lim nashriyoti, 2009. - 158 b.
2. Kizi, K. E. T., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2024). COMPARATIVE SEMANTIC STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Central Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 1(13), 69-74.
3. kizi Tohirova, M. A., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). BASIC LITERARY ELEMENTS OF THE XX CENTURY ENGLISH AND UZBEK SHORT STORIES (BASED ON HERBERT BATES AND SAID AHMAD’S SHORT STORIES). THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 192-195.
4. ugli Tojimurodov, H. Y., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). BEOWULF–THE EARLIEST EPIC POEM IN ENGLISH FOLKLORE. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 189-191.
5. kizi Aliyeva, G. A., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). ANALYSIS OF THE STORY ‘LUCKY ARTISTAND’BY ENGLISH AUTHOR SOMERSET MAUGHAM. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 172-175.
6. kizi Abdukodirova, K. A., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). LITERARY VERSION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND CHOOSING ITS TEACHING BALANCE. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 164-167.
7. kizi Abdullayeva, L. Z., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE IS “THE FATHER OF ENGLISH TRAGEDY”. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 168-171.
8. kizi Daulbayeva, J. R., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). UNFORGETTABLE MEMORIES OF CHILDHOOD THE ARTISTIC ANALYSIS OF THE NOVEL “KITE RUNNER” WRITTEN BY KHALID HUSAINI. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 181-183.
9. kizi Gadayeva, G. F., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). USEFUL CREATIVE TECHNIQUES PROPOSED FOR TEACHING CHILDREN. THE

ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 176-180.

10. kizi Usmonova, Y. N., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). SHAKESPEARE’S INFLUENCE ON OTHER AUTHORS. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 201-204.

11. Karimova V.M. Fikr tarbiyasi va mustaqil fikrlash. – T.: «Ma'rifat», 1999 y. – 15-18 b.

12. Shodiyev N.Sh, Shukrullaeva S. Talabalarni ma’naviy tarbiyaviy hayotga tayyorlash - T: Ma’naviyat, 2008. – 197 b.

13. E.T.Tursunnazarova “Pedagogikada innovatsiya”. “Umumta’lim fanlari metodikasi” ma’naviy-ma’rifiy, ilmiy, metodik nashr. 2019-yil/fevral № 2 (98)

14. Tursunnazarova E.T. Using different techniques to help learners understand and learn new words. // ilm-fan va ta’limning rivojlanish istiqbollari 3-konferensiya to‘plami. -Navoiy, 2020. -B. 75-77 b.